

Real Time Event Detection for Intelligent Building Surveillance System Application

(Pengesanan Peristiwa Masa Nyata untuk Aplikasi Sistem Pengawasan Bangunan Pintar)

Shahril Rizal Amru^a, Mohamad Hanif Md Saad^{b,c}, Noorfazila Kamal^{a,c*}, Aini Hussain^{a,c}

^aProgram of Electrical and Electronics Engineering,

^bProgram of Mechanical Engineering,

^cCentre for Integrated Systems Engineering and Advanced Technologies (INTEGRA)

Faculty of Engineering and Built Environment,

Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia.

ABSTRACT

Intelligent building surveillance system requires Complex Events Processing (CEP) based detection system to assist the intrusion detection for security reliability. However, almost all existing surveillance systems have limited self-learning ability that only allow real time monitoring and are unable to identify the actual events that take place in the monitored ambient. In this research, CAISER-MEGA is used as the engine of CEP to correlate raw data extracted from Closed Circuit Television (CCTV). Four classification techniques comprised of MEGA (Multilayered Event Detector for Generic Application), TCT (Temporally Constrained Template Match Detector), SWD (Sliding Window Detector) and WSD (Weighted sub-window Sliding Window Detector) via intelligent rule template matching algorithm are employed. These classifiers are used to detect complex event occurrence and they are influenced by the ambient noise. In this work, three different situation which are ideal situation, non-ideal situation and misaligned situation has been added in the sequence events using InVISS Event Annotator to assess the performance of the four classification techniques detection of complex events (CE) in real-world task. Confusion matrix and Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve are used in the classifiers performance evaluation to measure each classifier's efficiency. The results show that SWD classifier have highest value of Area Under Curve (AUC), but MEGA classifier has higher average accuracy value in predicting the complex event occurrence.

Keywords: Complex events; classification techniques; confusion matrix; Receiver Operating Characteristic curve

ABSTRAK

Sistem Pengawasan Bangunan Pintar memerlukan sistem pengesanan berasaskan pemprosesan peristiwa kompleks (CEP) untuk membantu pengesanan pencerobohan. Walau bagaimanapun, hampir semua sistem pengawasan yang ada pada hari ini mempunyai keupayaan pembelajaran-kendiri yang terhad yang hanya mempunyai fungsi pemantauan masa nyata dan tidak dapat mengesan peristiwa sebenar yang berlaku di dalam kawasan yang dipantau. Dalam kajian ini, CAISER-MEGA digunakan sebagai enjin CEP untuk mengaitkan data mentah yang diekstrak daripada televisyen litar tertutup (CCTV). Empat pengelasan terdiri daripada Pengesanan Peristiwa Multilayer untuk Aplikasi Generik (MEGA), Pengesanan Persamaan Templat Terkekang Sementara (TCT), Pengesanan Tetingkap Melungsur (SWD) dan Pengesanan Tetingkap Melungsur Tetingkap Sub-Berat (WSD) melalui pepadanan jujukan peristiwa digunakan. Keempat-empat pengelasan ini digunakan untuk mengesan kejadian peristiwa kompleks, dan ia dipengaruhi oleh gangguan hingar. Dalam kerja ini, tiga keadaan yang berbeza terdiri daripada keadaan ideal, keadaan tidak ideal dan keadaan tidak selaras ditambah dalam jujukan peristiwa dengan menggunakan InVISS.Annotator untuk menilai prestasi empat teknik pengelasan dalam melaksanakan pengesanan peristiwa kompleks pada situasi dunia sebenar. Matriks kekeliruan dan plot lengkung ciri operasi penerima (ROC) digunakan dalam penilaian prestasi teknik pengelasan bagi mengukur kecekapan setiap pengelasan. Keputusan menunjukkan pengelasan SWD mempunyai nilai Kawasan di bawah lengkung (AUC) tertinggi, tetapi pengelasan MEGA memberikan ketepatan purata yang lebih tinggi dalam membuat jangkaan kepada kejadian peristiwa kompleks.

Kata Kunci: peristiwa kompleks; teknik pengelasan; matrik kekeliruan; lengkung ciri operasi penerima

INTRODUCTION

Complex event processing (CEP) is processing of event which combines data from several sources to infer events or patterns that suggest more complicated circumstances. CEP is a field of research that raises research interest since in the past decade. The main goal of CEP is to identify meaningful events and respond to them as quickly as possible. According to Mehdiyev et al. (Mehdiyev et al. 2015), the main purpose of CEP is to detect complex event patterns from the atomic and semantically low-level events such as log, sensor or RFID data. The main task of CEP systems is determination of rule patterns for simple events matching based on the semantic, temporal or spatial correlations. Currently, event rule patterns in the CEP system are provided by experts. Later, automation in the CEP domain is required to fulfil demand from Internet of Things (IoT) technology and Big Data Systems. This can be done by implementation of advanced machine learning approaches in the CEP.

Although CEP is new, it has been successfully applied in several applications such as algorithmic stock-trading, fraud detection, business activity monitoring or sensor networks (Bruns & Dunkel, 2010). For example, Li et al. (Li & Bingwen 2010) introduced a CEP system that deploys network nodes computing power to reduce traffic waste due to communication data for wireless sensor network (WSN). The event processing queries, server and nodes' queries allow local real time event processing which help save network traffic and reduce chances of collision. Besides, Wang et al. (Wang et al. 2013) proposed a high performance hierarchical probabilistic CEP (PCEP) methodology that utilizes both tree-based query model and extended Nondeterministic Finite Automation (NFA) model to support complex event processing over single distributed event stream.

CEP also can be used as the key technology for intelligent Machine-to-Machine (M2M) systems (Bruns et al. 2015). M2M (machine-to-machine) systems use various communication technologies for automatically monitoring and controlling machines. In M2M systems, each machine emits a continuous stream of data records, which must be analysed in real-time. Intelligent M2M systems should be able to diagnose their actual states and to trigger appropriate actions as soon as critical situations occur.

A CEP engine analyses the stream of continuously incoming events and executes the matching rules. Event processing rules transform low level simple events into more complex events in order to gain insight into the current state of the environment. Open source CEP engines such as Drools Fusion (JBoss, 2014), Triceps (Babkin, 2014) and Esper (ESPERTECH, 2014) are commonly used. A system is called event driven if processing of events is the

central architectural concept of the software system, and the architectural style is known as event-driven architecture (EDA) (Chandy & Schulte, 2010; Bruns & Dunkel, 2010).

CEP has three core steps, namely filtering, matching and derivation. Filtering step attempts to define the lists of the relevant simple events which can be attributed as predictors. Matching step tries to identify the subset of simple events provided from previous step by analysing if they can fulfil the specific conditions of defined rule patterns, and derivation step detects more complex events using the information provided from matching subsets (Mehdiyev et al. 2015).

In order to detect complex event, machine-learning classifier can be used to replace the manual identification. In this work, four types of classifier are used, namely Multi-layered Event Detector for Generic Application (MEGA), Temporally Constrained Template Match Detector (TCD), Sliding Window Detector (SWD) and WSD (Weighted sub-window Sliding Window Detector (WSD)). Performance of these four classifiers are obtained and compared to determine which classifier is suitable to be used for CEP. In addition, each classifier is tested in three different conditions, namely ideal, non-ideal and misalign to test their operation in real-work task environment.

METHODOLOGY

Figure 1 shows the flowchart of proposed surveillance system.

FIGURE 1 Flowchart of the surveillance system

This research consists of three phase which are Phase I: Early set up, Phase II: Development and Phase III: Final test. Explanation for each phase is as below:

Phase I - The research is conducted in the Faculty of Engineering and Built Environment, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia. For event detection, three monitoring regions have been selected, namely R1, R2 and R3 as shown in Figure 2. In video surveillance systems, complex event detection consists of three activities, namely video events detection, target features description and semantic concept finding (Ke et al. 2016). This work focuses on analysing the effectiveness of four type of classifier techniques comprised of Multi-layered Event Detector for Generic Application (MEGA), Temporally Constrained Template Match Detector (TCD), Sliding Window Detector (SWD) and WSD (Weighted sub-window Sliding Window Detector (WSD)). Three different type of conditions, namely ideal, non-ideal and misaligned situations are added into the event sequences to test the classifiers in real-work task environment.

FIGURE 2. Region of interest

Phase II – In this phase, video captured is transferred to InVISS Event Annotator (Figure 3a) to be annotated in order to form sequence file which contain both simple and complex events that are inside the video. Then, a rule template file is generated in order to match the sequences events. Figure 3b shows the User Interface (UI) window of CAISER.MEGA. CAISER.MEGA will then receive data from InVISS Event Annotator. In CAISER.MEGA, the sequence file and rule template file will be matched using intelligent rule-based algorithm in order for the system to make decision. The sequence file undergoes a process called similarity matching with four different types of classifiers where the sequence file is matched with rule template file to evaluate the classifiers. The classifiers also tested by varying the confidence factor value from 0.00 to 1.00. Seven confidence factor value are used, namely 0.00, 0.20, 0.33, 0.50, 0.67, 0.80 and 1.00. In this work, four simple events are identified which are person moved at R1, person moved at R2, person moved at R3 and person fall at R3, as tabulated in Table 1. These four simple events lead to five complex events

which are survey ambient, loitering ambient, interact with ATM, falling ambient and injured, as tabulated in Table 2.

FIGURE 3a. User interface of InVISS Event Annotator

FIGURE 3b. User interface of CAISER.MEGA

TABLE 1. Simple event in this research

Simple events	Description
person.movedR1	Person moved at R1
person.movedR2	Person moved at R2
person.movedR3	Person moved at R3
person.fallR2	Person fall at R2

Phase III – In this phase, result from the similarity matching will show whether the event sequence is anomalous. If the event is anomalous, it will trigger the security system to send early warning or alarm, or else it will end the process. Confusion matrix and ROC plot is used in this work to measure the performance of each classifier working in three conditions as stated earlier. Performance for each classifier is compared to determine the best classifier to be used in CEP.

TABLE 2. Complex events of this research

Complex events	Level	Description
person.surveyambient	1	person.movedR1 → person.movedR2 → person.movedR2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Person survey in ambient
person.loiteringambient	1	person.movedR1 → person.movedR2 → person.movedR2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Person loitering in ambient
person.interactsATM	2	person.movedR1 → person.movedR2 → person.loiteringambient → person.movedR3 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Person interact with ATM
person.fallingambient	1	person.movedR1 → person.movedR2 → person.fallR2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Person fallen in ambient
person.injured	2	person.movedR1 → person.movedR2 → person.fallR2 → person.movedR2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Person injured in ambient

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A confusion matrix table have been built to assess the classifiers performance. Four metrics which are TPR (True Positive Rate), FPR (False Positive Rate), average accuracy and the area under the ROC (Receiver Operating Characteristic) curve plot (AUC) are used to evaluate the performance of classifier over complex event detection. The rule template matching procedure of all four classifiers is conducted using confidence factor value of 0.00, 0.20, 0.33, 0.50, 0.67, 0.80 and 1.00 for three conditions as mentioned in methodology. Table 3, 4 and 5 show the confusion matrix of MEGA, TCT, SWD and WSD classifiers for three conditions which have been tested. Next, ROC curve for the three conditions are plotted based on TPR and FPR values obtained from the confusion matrix in Table 3, 4 and 5. ROC curves are used to quantify the classifier performance. Figure 4, 5 and 6 show the ROC curve plot for ideal, non-ideal and misaligned conditions, respectively. Table 6 summarizes the result of the AUC for the four classifiers using *trapz* in Matlab, while Table 7 summarize the accuracy of each classifiers obtained through confusion matrix.

Based on the Table 3, 4 and 5, it is observed that confidence factor value affects the TPR and FPR value. Therefore, 0.00 confidence factor value is not suitable to detect complex events due to the outcome of very high FPR value which is 1.00, even though the TPR gives the same value. In overall, confidence factor affects sensitivity adjustment in the rule template file. The confidence factor value must be determined depending on the type of events that need to be detected, otherwise it will cost the result significantly.

Environment factor such as light will also affect the quality of classifier detection on complex events. Hence, three different conditions are introduced in this work to test and compare the performance of all four classifiers in real-world operating condition. Performance of each classifiers can be measured by Area Under the Curve (AUC) of the ROC plot as depicted in Table 6. Based on average AUC value, SWD has the best performance of event detection on these three conditions with average AUC value of 0.9925. It is follows by MEGA with average AUC value of 0.9822, then TCT with average AUC value of 0.98133. Finally, the WSD gives the least performance with average AUC value of 0.964. In addition, SWD also provides TPR closer to 1.00 with the increasing confidence factor value. Therefore, it can be inferred that SWD classifier performs better in complex event detection in ideal situation, when compared to other classifiers.

Table 6 shows that all classifiers produce high performance through event detection with average AUC value more than 0.96. However, in Table 7, MEGA have shown the highest average accuracy result in these three conditions. It shows that MEGA classifier is more accurate compared to other classifiers on performing real-work task, since MEGA classifiers have the highest average accuracy value in the three situations, which is 0.8139. Second highest average accuracy value is given by TCT classifier with 0.7964. This is follows by SWD with 0.707 average accuracy, and the least accurate classifier is given by WSD with only 0.5091 average accuracy.

TABLE 3. Confusion matrix for ideal condition

Confidence factor	MEGA		TCT		SWD		WSD	
	TPR	FPR	TPR	FPR	TPR	FPR	TPR	FPR
0.00	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
0.20	1.000	0.098	1.000	0.187	1.000	0.512	1.000	0.941
0.33	1.000	0.152	1.000	0.187	1.000	0.512	1.000	0.794
0.50	1.000	0.113	0.800	0.154	1.000	0.192	1.000	0.631
0.67	0.818	0.007	0.914	0.000	1.000	0.000	1.000	0.232
0.80	0.818	0.004	0.914	0.000	1.000	0.000	1.000	0.146
1.00	0.658	0.000	0.914	0.000	1.000	0.000	1.000	0.005

TABLE 4. Confusion matrix for non-ideal condition

Confidence factor	MEGA		TCT		SWD		WSD	
	TPR	FPR	TPR	FPR	TPR	FPR	TPR	FPR
0.00	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
0.20	0.982	0.078	1.000	0.149	1.000	0.402	1.000	0.822
0.33	0.945	0.067	1.000	0.149	1.000	0.402	1.000	0.646
0.50	0.688	0.045	0.971	0.092	1.000	0.104	1.000	0.457
0.67	0.549	0.006	0.783	0.003	0.795	0.000	1.000	0.161
0.80	0.549	0.004	0.783	0.003	0.795	0.000	1.000	0.103
1.00	0.386	0.001	0.783	0.003	0.795	0.000	0.986	0.044

TABLE 5. Confusion matrix for misalign condition

Confidence factor	MEGA		TCT		SWD		WSD	
	TPR	FPR	TPR	FPR	TPR	FPR	TPR	FPR
0.00	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
0.20	1.000	0.204	1.000	0.178	1.000	0.584	1.000	0.953
0.33	0.988	0.142	1.000	0.178	1.000	0.584	1.000	0.845
0.50	0.974	0.085	1.000	0.146	1.000	0.157	1.000	0.643
0.67	0.874	0.011	0.886	0.008	0.863	0.001	1.000	0.224
0.80	0.814	0.007	0.886	0.008	0.863	0.001	1.000	0.156
1.00	0.675	0.002	0.886	0.008	0.863	0.001	0.989	0.057

FIGURE 4. ROC plot for ideal condition

FIGURE 5. ROC plot for non-ideal condition

FIGURE 6. ROC plot for misalign condition

TABLE 6. Area Under the Curve (AUC) of the ROC plot

AUC	MEGA	TCT	SWD	WSD
Ideal condition (without noise)	0.9888	0.9747	1.000	0.9943
Non-ideal condition (additive noise)	0.9689	0.9852	0.9893	0.9556
Misalign condition	0.9890	0.9841	0.9883	0.9425
Average AUC	0.9822	0.98133	0.9925	0.9640

TABLE 7. Accuracy of each classifiers

Accuracy	MEGA	TCT	SWD	WSD
Ideal condition (without noise)	0.8103	0.7921	0.7007	0.4909
Non-ideal condition (additive noise)	0.8316	0.8060	0.7373	0.5600
Misalign condition	0.8000	0.7911	0.6828	0.4765
Average Accuracy	0.8139	0.7964	0.7070	0.5091

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

In this work, CEP-based algorithm and machine-

learning classifier is used to detect complex event in the monitored ambient. These technique helps to improve existing surveillance system. Four type of classifier techniques comprised of Multi-layered Event Detector for Generic Application (MEGA), Temporally Constrained Template Match Detector (TCD), Sliding Window Detector (SWD) and WSD (Weighted sub-window Sliding Window Detector (WSD) is used. Performance of these four classifiers in terms of TPR (True Positive Rate), FPR (False Positive Rate), average accuracy and the area under the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve plot (AUC) have been obtained and compared. The results show that SWD classifier have highest value of AUC. However, MEGA classifier has higher average accuracy value compared to SWD in predicting the complex event occurrence. Therefore, MEGA classifier is better in making decision on performing real-world task. However, the proposed system only considers a single camera view for visual monitoring, which highly influence the accuracy of movement detection in the region of interest. In addition, the system only limited to single people tracking in the building. Therefore, future research should focus on improving these limitations through better modeling and detection scheme.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to express gratitude to Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia and Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation (MOSTI) for supporting this research work. This study was financially supported by ScienceFund project 01-01-02-SF1386 entitled "Design and implementation of a parallelized complex event processing platform for internet of thong application".

REFERENCES

- Adi, A., Botzer, D., Nechushtai, G. & Sharon, G. 2006. Complex Event Processing for Financial Services. *IEEE Services Computing Workshops, 2006.* 7-12.
- Castro, J.L., Delgado, M., Medina, J. & Ruiz-Lozano, M.D. 2011. Intelligent surveillance system with integration of heterogeneous information for intrusion detection. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 38(9): 11182–11192.
- Mehdiyev, N., Krumeich, J., Enke, D., Werth, D. & Loos, P. 2015. Determination of Rule Patterns in Complex Event Processing Using Machine Learning Techniques. *Procedia - Procedia Computer Science*, 61: 395–401.
- Mehdiyev, N., Krumeich, J., Werth, D. & Loos, P. 2016. Determination of Event Patterns for Complex Event Processing Using Fuzzy Unordered Rule Induction Algorithm with Multi-objective Evolutionary Feature Subset Selection. *49th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS)*, 1719-1728.
- Rabiah Shahad, Mohamad Hanif, Ezra Lim Kai Xian. "Suspicious Loitering Detection form Annotated CCTV Feed using CEP based Approach" *Jurnal Kejuruteraan (UKM Engineering Journal)* 30(2) 83-91.
- Rabiah Shahad, Aini Hussain, Mohamad Hanif Md. Saad. Activity Recognition for Smart Building Application Using Complex Event Processing Approach *ResearchGate* www.researchgate.net/publication/3248488
- Saha, S. & Neogy, S. 2014. A case study on smart surveillance application system using WSN and IP webcam. *Applications and Innovations in Mobile Computing (AIMoC)*, 36–41.
- Saleh, O. & Sattler, K.-U. 2013. Distributed Complex Event Processing in Sensor Networks. *IEEE 14th International Conference on Mobile Data Management (MDM)*, 23–26.
- Sedky, M.H., Moniri, M. & Chibelushi, C.C. 2005. Classification of smart video surveillance systems for commercial applications. *IEEE International Conference on Advanced Video and Signal Based Surveillance Proceedings of AVSS 2005*, 638–643.
- Shahad, R. A., Saad, M.H.M & Hussain, A. 2016. Multi-Sensor Complex Surveillance Event Identification Using Hidden Markov, Internal Report, Bangi.
- Shah, P.G., Huang, X. & Sharma, D. 2010. Sliding window method with flexible window size for scalar multiplication on wireless sensor network nodes, *International Conference on Wireless Communication and Sensor Computing (ICWCSC)*, 1-6.
- Wang, Y.H., Cao, K. & Zhang, X.M. 2013. Complex event processing over distributed probabilistic event streams. *9th International Conference on Fuzzy Systems and Knowledge Discovery (FSKD)*, 66(10): 1489–1493.